

Barakayev Bahodir O'roqovich

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the "Physical culture and sports" department

Phone: 91 298 67 27

Abstract

This article discusses modern innovative technologies, their active use in sports and teaching physical education at school. The specific characteristics of each type, their positive aspects, and the effect on the student's health are described and explained in physical education classes.

Key words: innovative technologies, innovations, physical training, traditional technologies, non-traditional technologies, intensity, volleyball, basketball, static exercises, stretching, aqua aerobics, aqua aerobics, step aerobics, slide, bodybuilding.

The problem of protecting students' health has recently become increasingly important. The health of pupils is getting worse every year and the number of pupils exempted from physical education is increasing. Besides, many people are not interested in this science. Therefore, it is becoming more and more important for teachers to introduce new methods and evaluation criteria into their lessons, which is necessary to interest students. As a result, one of the primary tasks of a physical education teacher is to maintain and strengthen the health of schoolchildren. In solving this task, the use of health technologies such as fitness and aerobics, as well as the use of non-traditional health tools such as relaxation and breathing exercises, are of great importance. The current forms of physical education are outdated and its basic values are devalued.

In the modern world, innovative technologies are becoming increasingly popular and becoming more important. They are gradually being introduced into various fields such as science, culture, and education.

Innovations in education imply new methods of teaching, new ways of organizing classes, innovations in the organization of educational content, methods of evaluating educational results. Elements of innovative technologies can be divided into traditional and non-traditional methods.

We will consider traditional innovative technologies used in physical education classes.

Health technologies include:

- Physical exercises should be dosed taking into account the physical development of all students and their health groups;
- The temperature regime, ventilation of the room, the place of physical education should be strictly controlled;
- The condition of sports equipment should be monitored and repaired on time;

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- Condition of sports clothes should be checked;
- Using special exercises to keep the body straight and prevent and correct vision;
- Using a method that includes alternation of intensity and relaxation in education;
- Performing wet cleaning in the gym.

Society is developing and today there is a need to use new information and communication technologies in various spheres of human activity. Accordingly, a modern school should not lag behind the requirements of the times. This means that a modern teacher should use information and communication technologies in his practice. Because the primary task of the school is to educate a knowledgeable, independent, thinking generation.

We live in the age of information technology, and the teacher must keep up with the times. Therefore, in his work, he can use various programs, take into account the results, conduct computer tests. Also, a teacher can create his own website in order to spread his experience, provide sample visual aids in classes, find information for methodical, research and project work.

The use of an interactive whiteboard helps facilitate the teaching of technically complex sports such as volleyball and basketball in physical education classes. In the process of using the blackboard, the teacher can divide a certain technical method into slides and show it to the students at a pace they understand. In addition, if necessary, there is an opportunity to stop at one of the slides and explain the method in more detail. While the slides are being shown, you can use a special marker to show the directions of the hands, feet and body movements with sticks. Markers and sticks can also be used to show, for example, what the direction of the ball might be if the hands and feet are not working properly. This method of teaching technical movements is very effective and popular with students because it is taught in a visual way.

As for competition technologies, they allow students to fully express themselves in individual competitions. In addition, it helps them to improve the efficiency of working with the team. One type of lesson is competition lessons. After studying each topic, such lessons can be conducted. Pupils exempted from physical education lessons or children assigned to a special group due to health can participate as referees.

Game technologies are used in almost every lesson. They can be conducted in the form of an educational game at the end of each lesson. There are many action games based on volleyball, basketball and many other games. The more varied the games are, the more students will be interested in the lesson.

Level differentiation technology involves testing the physical fitness of schoolchildren at different levels. It is advisable to conduct such tests twice a year. In the main group of physical education, both school children and children with poor health can be given different tasks. Special education technology can also be included in this. This technology is especially relevant for students of adolescent age (seventh-ninth grades). At this age, physical differences between boys and girls become more apparent due to physiological changes. This requires a differential approach to training. We consider it appropriate to use special educational elements in physical education classes. This technology can be implemented if physical education teachers work together in classrooms. For example, girls can learn gymnastics with elements of acrobatics, while boys can improve football and volleyball techniques. If the lessons are organized in this way, the interests of boys and girls are taken into account.

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We will consider innovative innovative technologies used in physical education classes.

Another non-traditional innovative technology used in physical education classes can be Nordic walking (walking with sticks). This technology is especially relevant for children with poor health.

The ancient Chinese gypsy art can also be included in non-traditional innovative technologies. These exercises are divided into three classes according to the method of execution:

- 1) static exercises (they are sometimes called quiet);
- 2) dynamic exercises (i.e. moving);
- 3) static-dynamic exercises (combination of motionless states and movements).

These exercises help you learn to regulate your body, breathing, and mind, or a combination of these.

It is a system of physical exercises developed by scientists in the early 20th century to rehabilitate people after injuries. Currently, this set of exercises is actively used in school practice. They help develop the endurance of certain muscle groups and can be beneficial for those with spinal cord injuries.

Also, types of fitness technologies: stretching, aqua aerobics, step-aerobics, slide, bodybuilding are highlighted.

Stretching is a form of fitness and is a set of exercises that help stretch the muscles and connective tissues of the body.

Aqua aerobics is a type of gymnastics performed in water to rhythmic music. Nowadays, many schools are equipped with a swimming pool, because the third hour of physical education is included in general education institutions. This is related to the need to increase the importance of physical education and strengthen the health of students.

Oriental practices are also non-traditional innovative technologies used in physical education classes. Examples include yoga and tai chi.

It is worth noting the portfolio technology. The purpose of this is to ensure that students have a certain experience in collecting, systematizing and presenting results and achievements in the subject of "Physical Education". By creating and maintaining a portfolio, the dynamics of physical fitness indicators of students are observed, it helps to achieve success, increase self-confidence and develop interest in physical education.

The functional necessity of pedagogues in educational institutions is the application of innovations in the system of educating students with physical education. The use of innovative technologies in physical education implies a creative approach to the pedagogical process, the main goal of which is to increase students' interest in physical education and sports. This is probably the main goal that should be achieved, because improving the efficiency of the educational process is the main task for maintaining the health of students.

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